

Developments towards a Humanism 2.0

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Abstract

This working paper presents the positions of humanism and veganism in order to demonstrate that, under certain conditions, both could potentially give rise to a new form of "Humanism 2.0."

While existing fundamental differences between humanism and veganism are acknowledged, this article outlines the differences that exist and proposes a potential course of action.

1. Introduction

What are the shared principles between humanism and veganism? Some humanist currents still exhibit a latent specialism that places people at the center but does not see them as part of the entire living world. Christoph Maria Herbst, a prominent actor and self-confessed vegan, even commented on the publication of a new book on animal ethics that humanism was now being redefined as "animalism" (cf. Sezgin 2014: 3).

Richard Kahn, University of North Dakota, acknowledges that an interdisciplinary posthumanist discourse is giving rise to new fields of study such as "human-animal studies," which could be perceived as an opportunity to break with the long tradition of specialized research. However, he expresses concern that posthumanism or other fields of study that distance themselves from the requirements of a consistent liberation of animals from previous paradigms could hardly do more than undermine animal viewpoints, at least as long as they limit their goals in favor of professional prestige and conservative political views (cf. Kahn 2011: 66).

It can be argued that a humanism that regards humans as part of the world and no longer as its crowning glory does not necessarily require rewriting as "transhumanism" or

"animalism" (as opposed to "hominism"). This question can now be answered in the negative, as more and more humanist thinkers and researchers have already overcome the anthropocentric paradigm.

2. Examples of approaches

The following examples present the work of Frans de Waal, Martha Nussbaum, Hilal Sezgin, Harry Kunneman, and Henk Manschot.

2.1 Empathy and cooperation promote coexistence: de Waal

Empathy, cooperation, fairness, and reciprocity are considered typical human traits. However, concern for the well-being of others seems to be a peculiarity of our species. Frans de Waal refers to behavioral tests in primates and other mammals that demonstrate how many of their moral traits we share (see TED 2013).

The Dutch primatologist, who currently resides in the United States, has identified a number of behavioral patterns that are typically human among primates. These include the way in which they interact with disabled conspecifics (cf. de Waal 2013).

In his book *The Empathy Principle*, Frans de Waal posits that the mechanism for empathy between different species is activated by the other species. He argues that social Darwinists have learned the wrong lessons from nature.

The norms of animals living in social groups are characterized by a lack of fierce competition, ruthless exploitation, and deceit. Instead, they exhibit a preference for cooperation, mediation, and empathy towards other members of their social group. (Cf. de Waal 2011)

2.2 Skills need to be exercised: Nussbaum

The American philosopher Martha Nussbaum also builds a bridge between humans and animals, as she perceives similarities in the manner in which humans and animals desire to live. Her so-called capabilities approach, which defines a successful human life as one in which central capabilities can be exercised, implies that these capabilities can be determined across cultures.

Nussbaum enumerates life, health, integrity, the use of one's own mind, emotional life, entering into social relationships, control over one's own environment, and play as the fundamental elements of a flourishing life. She posits that these elements should be considered in the context of a certain conception of human dignity and a life in accordance with this dignity, which she defines as a life that opens up the possibility of "truly human activity" (Nussbaum 2010: 110).

Martha Nussbaum, who was awarded an honorary doctorate from the Universiteit voor Humanistiek (UvH) in Utrecht in 2009, was recognized for her contributions to the field of human dignity. In her work, she addressed crucial issues related to the concept of dignity, including its application to animals. She subsequently applied her theory to animals, as evidenced by her writings (cf. Nussbaum 2010: 484; 528 ff.).

2.3 Taking the abilities and needs of all seriously: Sezgin

The German philosopher and animal ethicist Hilal Sezgin takes up Nussbaum's list of ten abilities in relation to animals and suggests adding the point "performing species-specific activities." By this, she understands typical behavioral patterns of free-living animals (cf. Sezgin 2014: 187f.).

Sezgin emphasizes that Nussbaum's approach is compatible with biological theory and that animals are understood here as living beings with abilities and needs that they wish to exercise and satisfy (cf. Nussbaum 2010: 188).

2.4 Towards an anthropocosmic paradigm: Kunneman, Manschot

In his analysis, Harry Kunneman identifies neoliberalism as a key factor in the reduction of individuals' perception of the potential for free individuals to develop alternative forms of life on earth.

On the one hand, this is accomplished by continuously reducing biodiversity and the populations of plants and animals. On the other hand, it is also done existentially by imposing an industrialized way of life on a vast number of chickens, pigs, cows, and fish, in which their lives are reduced to growing as quickly as possible in an industrially desired form and direction in order to be used economically as effectively as possible (cf. Kunneman 2013: 9).

As posited by humanism researcher Henk Manschot, the distinction between humans and other living beings on earth has become one of the two fundamental principles underlying the contemporary view of the relationship between humans and the rest of the world.

The second of the two principles was a technological and instrumentalizing attitude towards these other living beings. This, in turn, led to humans being treated as objects or used as instruments (cf. Manschot 2009: 64 f.). He critiques the fact that the view of human development has become detached from a holistic view of the larger community of life, the biosphere. He calls for the central values of humanity to be rethought from the perspective of this larger community of life, suggesting a transition from an anthropocentric to an anthropocosmic world view (cf. Manschot 2009: 67).

He delineates three orienting approaches that should facilitate the transition from a human-centered to a cosmo-centered worldview (cf. Manschot 2009: 68):

- an evolutionary view that leads to an evaluation of modernity in the broader context of cosmogenesis;
- an extension of man's responsibility for all life on this planet and not just for his own species;
- as well as the demand for meaningful institutions of worldview and culture to explicitly engage with this transformation.

3. Securing the Future

For other researchers, the future prospects of their planet are also contingent upon and in conflict with the needs of the earth's human inhabitants. There is little reason to believe that non-human animals will jeopardize these prospects. However, there is a greater concern that humans will do so, given their unrestricted reproductive capacity and the increasingly resource-consuming nature of their diet.

The topic of nutrition is not addressed by the humanist authors cited above, despite its unquestionable importance in the utilization of the earth, its living creatures, the economy, and ecology.

A suitable humanistic starting point would be helpful here in order to also examine people's nutrition-oriented value systems, which ultimately cannot be treated independently of the more fundamental questions of human welfare, animal welfare, animal protection, and the ethics of dealing with other living beings.

An alternative approach would be to elucidate the potentialities of "sufficiency" in contrast to growth-oriented "efficiency." Nutritionist Toni Meier has compiled a compendium of instruments and methods, as well as environmental impact categories relevant to nutrition, which she has employed to produce useful results (see Meier 2014). Furthermore, these tools could be beneficial for the humanistic discourse.

3.1 Ecological responsibility

Henk Manschot posits that the concept of human responsibility for the life of all on earth is already present in numerous initiative groups that are committed to ecological revitalization and for whom humanism could be a source of inspiration. According to Manschot, humanism is inextricably linked to the modern values of freedom, autonomy, and human worth.

A potential avenue for bridging the divide between modernity and the future is thus opened up. Manschot even posits the possibility of a humanistic-cosmological perspective, which could represent a genuine paradigm shift (cf. Manschot 2009: 80).

3.2 Common motives

In light of the aforementioned positions of contemporary humanists, particularly in light of the humanistic-cosmological approach, several similarities can be observed in the fundamental motives underlying these perspectives.

This is because those who adhere to a holistic vegan lifestyle or worldview typically cite the following motives for their dietary choices (cf. Grube 2006: 4), although these motives do not typically represent the primary motivating factors for each individually:

- The ethical and moral motives of vegans include compassion for animals, equal treatment of humans and animals, and opposition to speciesism.
- Health motives include preventing or curing illnesses, increasing performance and well-being, and reducing the risk of disease transmission.
- Ecological motives include overfishing, water pollution, the greenhouse effect, and deforestation of the rainforest due to overgrazing.
- Economic motives include the cost of meat production and the impact of meat consumption on the environment. For example, the global distribution of raw materials is a contributing factor to the world hunger problem. Additionally, consumption avoidance is a motivating factor.

- Religious motifs include the perception of killing as an injustice or sin, as well as the taboo on eating meat. Spiritual powers are also released through the consumption of meat.

This analysis will identify shared positions and values between vegans and non-vegans. It will suggest that veganism should be discovered as part of the humanist discourse and given a sustainable place there.

4. A "Humanism 2.0"

In December 2013, the German Vegetarian Federation (VEBU) estimated that there were 800,000 vegans in Germany. However, in May 2014, this figure was revised upwards to 1.2 million, representing a 50% increase. This equates to 1.5% of the German population now identifying as vegan.

A significant proportion of these individuals can be observed in numerous Facebook groups, where it is evident that their dietary choices are not the only aspect of their lives undergoing transformation. However, the coexistence of humans and animals and the responsibility of humans for the life of all living beings on earth (see Manschot above under 4.) are not at the forefront of their perception in the major Western religious communities.

Consequently, the humanist movement in Germany and internationally may gain increasing appeal and interest from the ranks of vegans if it takes up Manschot's anthropocosmic design and develops it academically, also with a view to the motivations of the vegan movement, into "Humanism 2.0."

The pivotal issue is the extent to which humanistic researchers can relinquish the anthropocentric worldview in favor of a perspective that regards humans as one living being among many others. This entails a shift from a dominant to a protective role.

5. Researching vegan communication

Further research and subsequent publications will focus on the investigation of existing vegan and humanistic communication, as well as the development of new communication

designs and media concepts in the context of a proposed Humanism 2.0. This research employs the scientific methods and sources of human studies.

A publication series on such communication research could introduce the pillars and concepts of veganism as an object of investigation in the context of humanistic communication.

It will be a period of time before the most recent findings can be collated and presented.

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